

INVESTIGATING THE LEVEL OF RESILIENCE & IT'S IMPACT ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AMONG ADULTS

Muhammad Omar Khan¹, Ellma Rafiq², Umama Ahmed³

¹BS Scholar, Department of Applied Psychology, National University of Modern Languages, Karachi Campus, Pakistan.

^{2,3}Lecturer, Department of Applied Psychology, National University of Modern Languages, Karachi Campus, Pakistan.

¹omarniazi39@gmail.com, ²ellma.rafiq@numl.edu.pk, ³umama.ahmed@numl.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *

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ABSTRACT

Background: The heightened attention and understanding, which defines the Level of Resilience, and its considerable usefulness for promoting better Psychological Well-Being among Adults (Harding et al., 2019). Resilience is a personality trait that moderates stress and enhances adaptability, enabling individuals to cope with challenges without resorting to harmful behaviors. Resilient individuals manage emotions effectively, maintain a positive outlook, and use problem-solving skills to address adversity. This trait contributes significantly to Psychological Well-Being by improving emotional health, adaptability, and interpersonal relationships, while also supporting physical health and achievement. Age Factor also play a significant role in betterment of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults. The current research asses the importance of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor in mitigating stress and promoting Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Pakistani adults.

Objective: The current study aims to examine the impact of the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on the Psychological Well-Being (PWB) (according to Ryff's (1989) perspective of Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being) in a sample of 193 Pakistani adults aged range from 18 to 35 [Male (m): 97 and Female (f): 96] coming from diverse educational or professional backgrounds. The current study aims to answer the following research questions in context Pakistani adults: RQ1- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ2- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ3- Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ4- Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)?

Methods: The current study employ Cross-sectional survey method for data collection study, which means data is collected at one specific point in time from participants using Demographic Information Form to collect Socio-Demographic characters of participants such as Age Factor, Gender, Questionnaires such as the Brief Resilience Scale (6-Items) (Smith et al., 2008) to measure the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Psychological Well-Being Scale (42-Items) (Ryff & Keyes, 1995) to measure Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of participants. Descriptive Statistics was run in SPSS to assess Socio-Demographic Information of Participants, Pearson Product Correlation of SPSS 2022 for analyzing association and Multiple Linear Regression Test to assist the impact of the Level of Resilience, Age Factor on Psychological Well-Being among Adults.

Results: Findings indicated that Level of Resilience is a Significant Positive Predictor for overall Psychological Well-Being of adults and also for its Core Six-Dimensions especially for Autonomy and Environmental Mastery. Furthermore, Age Factor is weak Predictor for Overall Psychological Well-Being of Adults and Age Factor has no significant correlation with Purpose in Life-Dimension of Psychological Well-Being and Positive Relations with Others appears to be significantly correlated with Age in Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB).

Conclusion: Current research significantly contributes to literature for future researches in context of Psychological Well-Being and Level of Resilience of Pakistani adults, because limited literature is available on this topic. Current research can facilitate researcher who are keenly interested in developing Resilience-Focused techniques to address psychopathology and promotes Psychological Well-Being among adults by providing an insightful literature about this association.

Keywords: Level of Resilience, Psychological Well-Being, Resilient Adults

INTRODUCTION

Present days, the term “Resilience” has been a topic of interest for researchers. The American Psychological Association defines resilience as “the process of adapting well in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threats, or even significant sources of stress”. (1, para. 4) While this definition is useful, it does not reveal the complex nature of resilience. (2) There are multiple definitions of resilience, and it is surrounded by many controversies and diversities. Resilience is defined as a process (3-4), outcome (5-6), and personality trait (7-9). Despite these differences, in general terms, most definitions of resilience describe it as overcoming risk factors and demonstrating positive emotions and behavior in a situation of adversity (10). Resilience pertains to an individual’s ability to withstand, adapt, and recuperate from adversity and stress. Resilience is a class of phenomenon characterized by good outcomes despite serious threats to adaptation or development (11, p. 228). Resilience is indicated when individuals demonstrate good mental health despite exposure to significant stress or adversity. Good mental health may involve low levels of ill-being and high levels of well-being. Resilience can also be defined as “maintenance, recovery, or improvement in mental or physical health following challenge”. (12, p. 20) Across the life span, we all encounter adversities and challenges. These adversities have a significant impact on our life, happiness, and well-being. Resilience or hardness are the personality characteristics that respond to adverse life events. In some literature, resilience is defined as a psychological process in which individuals make use of many positive factors to maintain and develop their physical and mental health to find well-being in their lives when they are faced with

various pressures, setbacks, or difficulties. (13) Masten (11) notes that some researchers have also defined resilience as an absence of problem behaviors or psychopathology following adversity. Challenges and changes are part of life; dealing with them is a person’s ability to cope, adapt, or bounce back in the face of adversities. In life, individuals face varying degrees of challenges; some might be insignificant or minor, for instance, getting scolded by a teacher for not being on time; in contrast, some might have a significant impact on life that changes the life of an individual, for example, experiencing a pandemic, a global crisis, a terrorist attack, and divorce or losing beloved ones. Adaptability displays proficiency to handle life challenges and is an overall representation of rigidity. The potential in people to remain calm in the face of adversity is what psychologists call adaptability. People with adaptability can use their chops and strengths to manage and recover from life’s challenges, which can include drastic stressors such as the death of a loved one, divorce, financial issues, illness, job loss, medical extremities, natural disasters, etc. According to the positive psychology viewpoint, resilience is a person’s ability to cope with whatever life throws at them. Some people go through hardships and misfortune and develop attributes that help them cope with adverse life events; these people are called resilient. The psychological well-being (PWB) of resilient people is a fundamental topic of study in the current age. The relationship between PWB and resilience is one of the most interesting topics in educational positive psychology in different domains of human development and according to the life-span perspective. (14) Ryff & Singer (12) argued that resilient individuals were generally capable of

maintaining their physical and psychological health and could recover more quickly from stressful events. Specifically, we deepened the construct of resilience defined as “a personality characteristic that moderates the negative effects of stress and promotes adaptation” (8) and as “the ability to restore or maintain internal or external equilibrium under significant threat employing human activities including thought and action”. (15)

In the 20th century, psychologist Carol Ryff (14) developed a very clear model that breaks down psychological well-being into six different faces. This psychological well-being concept about happiness and well-being is also referred to as eudaimonic well-being or happiness, which can also be traced back to the idea of eudaimonia by Aristotle during the Greek period. The literal meaning of the Greek word eudaimonia is the state of ‘good spirit’ and is mostly translated in literature as “happiness” or welfare. In older Greek tradition, the term eudaimonia was for the highest human good. Greek philosopher Aristotle’s idea of eudaimonia forms the basis for the concept of Psychological Well-Being (PWB). (16-17) The construct of psychological well-being argues that the experience of feeling expressiveness as a result of engaging in actions consistent with one’s true potential and pursuit of intrinsic goals (18-21). As a life-span developmental psychologist, Carol Ryff works on Aristotle’s idea of happiness and conceptualizes the term Psychological Well-Being. Numerous theorists elaborated on the ideas about human growth and development. These theories were valuable for explaining the developmental tasks and challenges that individuals encounter at different stages of life. Theories such as Allport’s maturity criterion (22), Frankl’s search for meaning and logotherapy (23), hierarchy of needs and conceptualization of the term self-actualization (24), and optimal functioning or fully functioning person (25) from humanistic and existential approaches are quite permanent at that time in literature.

Based on this theoretical framework, Carol Ryff and her associates proposed one of the more comprehensive and scientifically validated models of well-being (12,26-28). The psychological well-being (PWB) model is composed of six dimensions of a person’s life, and these six dimensions are linked with the concept of

resilience or predictive of resilient responses in the face of adversity, successful aging, and the maintenance of good mental health (12,27). To put it succinctly, the six dimensions of the psychological well-being (PWB) model delineate facets of a person’s personality, self-perception or concept, competence, and interpersonal connections or social relationships that serve as assets for a successful life. The six dimensions of the psychological well-being model: environmental mastery, self-acceptance, personal growth, autonomy, purpose of life, and positive relations with others are described as follows: *A) Autonomy:* People who are autonomous feel at ease exercising initiative, working on their own, and being self-directed. These individuals have internal norms that direct their behavior and enable them to withstand harmful social demands from others. A sense of autonomy would be demonstrated by being who you are and sticking to your principles and passions. Goodwill towards Others. *B) Environmental Mastery:* A sense of expertise and the capacity to handle the complicated surroundings of today’s fast-paced lifestyle are referred to as mastery of the environment. Mastery is reflected in an individual’s ability to create a personally suitable living situation, including efficiently managing work, family, finances, shelter, health, education, and all the other necessities for a successful life. *C) Self-Acceptance:* An individual who possesses self-acceptance is one who views themselves positively and accepts every facet of who they are, flaws and all. Such a person feels positive about his or her life so far. *D) Purpose of Life:* Having an objective, values, motives, and goals that guide a person’s life means having a purpose in life. It could be anything that provides direction to an individual’s life, such as a person’s commitment to the welfare of humanity, religious convictions, career, or family that gives meaningful purpose to create change or live a successful life. *E) Personal Growth:* Personal growth pertains to an individual’s perception of their ongoing progress and efficacy, as well as their receptiveness to novel experiences and obstacles. A person who continues to be enthusiastic about life and learning new things is demonstrating personal growth. *F) Positive relations with others:* Individual’s interpersonal relationships are built by communicating with others in a warm, satisfying, and trustworthy manner and are

empathetic and intimate. Positive relations refer to the quality rather than the quantity of our relationships. Having good friends, a satisfying marriage, and supportive relations with co-workers all express this dimension.

According to Ryff & Singer (16-17,29), core dimensions such as Purpose in Life, and Personal Growth is linked with Age of adults or successful transitions during developmental stages. These dimensions of Psychological Well-Being are associated with sense of direction of adults or goal in life such as achieve or create something new or being productive that leads towards emotional integration in later life, continue to develop as a person, and expand your own horizon and achieve an optimal Psychological functioning, which underlines the significance of new tasks or challenges at different stages of life. (16,29) According to the findings of De-Juanas et al., (30) study on individuals aged from 16 to 21 from Spain, Bogotá and Madrid revealed that Age has a significant moderate positive correlation with Purpose in Life but this study done on individuals who live in individualistic culture or society that is quite opposite of collectivistic culture in which individuals are interdependent on each other in many aspects of life regardless of Age as compare to Individualistic culture where Age plays vital role to become independent in many aspects of life such as decisions making and deciding profession or career to pursue, purpose in life and also indicated that Autonomy is highly correlated with age.

Taking into account the complex nature of psychological well-being, it is necessary to find predictors of Psychological Well-Being through research rather than depending only on the studies that explain positive affect, life satisfaction or resilience, and psychological well-being alone. While talking about resilience as a predictor of psychological well-being, one study reported that the majority of adolescents can overcome negative emotions and face those hard times; thus, they are relatively competent to handle the condition and improve in positive functioning. (31) This study gives the idea that encountering adversities might increase the Level of Resilience in an individual and that increasing the Level of Resilience might play a role in tackling adversities and promoting healthy functioning means better Psychological Well-Being. While dipping into more positive psychology literature, some more significant

studies also found proposed internal and external resource protective factors of psychological well-being in the face of adversity. According to the study, the external factor is social support, for example, support from family, friends, and significant others, while internal factors consist of resilience, self-efficacy, and mindfulness. (32)

Resilience is defined as one's personal qualities that enable an individual to thrive when facing adversity in life. (9) Additionally, one of Richardson's (33) famous meta-theory articles, Interpret Resilience using **innate resilience**, refers to motivational forces within individuals and groups that are activated by specific experiences and drive them toward resiliently reintegrated from disruption. Precisely, the aspect of resilience consists of high standards, tenacity, personal competence, trust in one's instincts, strengthening effects of stress, tolerance of negative affect, positive acceptance of change, control, spiritual influences, and secure relationships. (9) Furthermore, Harding et al. (32) study also point out that resilience promotes psychological well-being by facilitating people to experience growth after stressful life events. Additionally, other studies also validated these findings by proposing that changes in life, rumination, and insight, which are part of the post-traumatic growth process, also contribute to promoting psychological well-being. (20-21,34) Hence, it is significant to prove whether the Level of Resilience effects the Psychological Well-Being of an individual by considering the further-explained theories and studies.

The heightened attention and understanding, which defines the Level of Resilience, and its considerable usefulness for promoting better Psychological Well-Being among Adults plays a pivotal role in background of the current study. (32) The current study explores the Psychological Well-Being of Resilient Adults and how the Level of Resilience and Age Factor predicts the overall Psychological Well-Being of individuals, and its core Six Dimensions (according to Ryff's (14) model). The current study will first explore the correlation between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults, and then it also explores which dimension has a significant correlation with these factors to get deeper understanding of this relationship. Additionally, we assess whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor has a

significant positive or negative impact on overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) and it's all Six Dimensions among adults. "Psychological well-being is attained by achieving a state of balance affected by both challenging and rewarding life events."⁽²¹⁾ And Resilience is a personality trait that moderates stress and enhances adaptability, enabling individuals to cope with challenges without resorting to harmful behaviors. ⁽⁸⁻⁹⁾ Resilient individuals manage emotions effectively, maintain a positive outlook, and use problem-solving skills to address adversity. This trait contributes significantly to Psychological Well-Being by improving emotional health, adaptability, and interpersonal relationships, while also supporting physical health and achievement. Age Factor also play a significant role in betterment of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults. The current asses the importance of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor in mitigating stress and promoting Psychological Well-Being among Pakistani adults. The current study aims to answer the following research questions in context Pakistani adults: RQ1- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ2- Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ3- Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? RQ4- Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? So, the study explores the impactful relationship between Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Pakistani adults.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Current quantitative research will employ cross-sectional survey research techniques to test the hypothesis. A current survey will collect data in a snapshot in time from Pakistani adults to investigate the Level of Resilience and Age Factor and its impact on their Psychological Well-Being (PWB).

Participants

Current study participants are young Pakistani adults [Age range: 18 - 35, Number of participants (N): 193, Females (f): 96, Male (m):

97]. For instance, this sampling may involve collecting data from individuals of various ages or developmental levels to study behavioral or other differences among them. Participants are from various backgrounds. For example, working or studying in different institutions and settings, or in different positions or levels. The current study will address the limitations of previous studies that associated the level of resilience with the population coming from a specific background. For instance, studies that target individuals who have been exposed to any disaster, such as the COVID-19 pandemic ⁽³⁵⁻³⁹⁾, or any adverse/stressful life event, such as children who have suffered from parent's marital dissolution ⁽⁴⁰⁾, or death of parents means children who are orphans ⁽⁴¹⁾, early life stress exposure ⁽⁴²⁾, or parents with mental or physical health problems, for example, schizophrenia, depression, or cancer ⁽⁴³⁻⁴⁴⁾, or who are prematurely born ⁽⁴⁵⁾. Simply, it means they define these traits as "heroic" and only explicitly found in these individuals. Since, the current study will address the shortcomings of these researches because the well-known theorist and the founder of resilience research, Norman Garmezy ⁽⁴⁶⁾, stated that "resilience is not necessarily impervious to stress. Rather, resilience is designed to reflect the capacity for recovery and maintained adaptive behavior that may follow initial retreat or incapacity upon initiating a stressful event." Additionally, he also points out that every child experiences stress at some point, and resilient children are not "the heroic ones," in contrast to those children who "meet similar situations with retreat, despair, or disorder" ⁽⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸⁾. So, it means resilience is not the trait of individuals who have experienced traumatic or stressful life events. This research will collect data from participants by taking into account the Garmezy point ⁽⁴⁷⁾ view about resilience by not simply associating the resilience trait with individuals who had experienced sufficient trauma or stress but collecting data from adults without classifying them into a category. Since this resilience trait is not specific to vulnerable individuals, but every individual has their level of resilience, it is beneficial to find the level of resilience in individuals without categorizing them as survivors of trauma or stressful life events and assess its effects on their psychological well-being.

Measures and Procedure

Participants will be recruited from diverse demographic backgrounds to examine the Level of Resilience (LOR) and its impact on Psychological Well-Being. Firstly, participants will be informed about the purpose of the study, assured about the confidentiality and privacy of their data, and asked for voluntary participation and signing of an informed consent form (a formal contract with participants to assure them they can withdraw at any time during the study). After obtaining informed consent, participants will complete a demographic information form followed by self-report measures that are Brief Resilience Scale (6-Items) (49) to assess their Level of Resilience (LOR) and Psychological Well-Being Scale (42-Items) (26) to assess their Psychological Well-Being (PWB). Subsequently, the responses of participants will be analyzed and interpreted to check whether the hypothesis is correct or not. Interpretation and analysis involve developing insight into the association between the Level of Resilience (LOR) and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) and the impact of the Level of Resilience (LOR) on the betterment of the Psychological Well-being (PWB) of participants.

The responses of participants that are collected by utilizing these measures will be analyzed, scored, and interpreted by using manuals and guides for these measures. Relevant descriptions of these measures and forms are discussed as follows:

1. Brief Resilience Scale (6-Items)

Items: 6 items, “I have a hard time making it through stressful events.”

Author: Smith, B. W., Dalen, J., Wiggins, K., Tooley, E., Christopher, P., & Bernard, J.

Year: 2008

Psychometrics: Cronbach's alpha: 0.80 to 0.9. (49)

2. Ryff's Psychological Well-Being scale (14-Items from 84-Items)

Items: 14 items, e.g., “In general, I feel confident and positive about myself.”

Author: Carol D. Ryff and Keyes

Year: 1995

Psychometrics: Cronbach's alpha: 0.93 to 0.86 and test-retest reliability over six weeks returned coefficients: 0.88 to 0.81, suggesting that responses to the questionnaire remain fairly consistent over time in the absence of intervention. Overall, these findings suggest the questionnaire is significantly reliable (50).

Statistical Analysis

The SPSS 2022 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software will be used for administering the data. Descriptive Statistic Descriptive Statistics was run in SPSS to assess Socio-Demographic Information of Participants, Pearson Product Correlation of SPSS 2022 for analyzing association and Regression Test to assist the impact of the Level of Resilience on Psychological Well-Being among Adults.

RESULTS

Findings indicated that Level of Resilience is a Significant Positive Predictor for overall Psychological Well-Being of adults and also for its Core Six-Dimensions especially for Autonomy and Environmental Mastery. Furthermore, Age Factor is weak Predictor for Overall Psychological Well-Being of Adults and Age Factor has no significant correlation with Purpose in Life-Dimension of Psychological Well-Being and Positive Relations with Others appears to be significantly correlated with Age in Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Research Participants

	Minimum	Maximum	M	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	SE	SE	
Age Factor	1.00	2.00	1.22	.41	1.38	.18	-.1	.35
Gender	1.00	2.00	1.50	.50	.10	.18	-2.02	.35
Educational Level	1.00	4.00	2.93	.72	-.15	.18	-.42	.35
Employment Status	1.00	6.00	3.33	1.70	-.25	.18	-1.57	.35
Marital Status	1.00	5.00	1.25	.60	3.54	.17	16.84	.35

Household Members	1.00	5.00	4.58	.79	-2.19	.18	5.12	.35
Living Status	1.00	3.00	2.22	.89	-.45	.18	-1.60	.35
Engage in Stress-Reducing Techniques	1.00	2.00	1.72	.45	-.99	.18	-1.03	.35

Note. $N = 193$ (97 Male and 96 Female Participants). Table summarize the descriptive statistics for the Socio-Demographics variables of participants in the current study, including Sample size (N), *Maximum* and *Minimum* values, Mean (M), Standard Deviation (SD), *Skewness*, *Kurtosis*, and Standard Error (SE) values for both Skewness and Kurtosis.

Table 2

Correlation between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) Among Adults

	<i>Level of Resilience (LoR)</i>	<i>Psychological Well-Being (PWB)</i>
Level of Resilience (LoR)	-	.53**
Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)	.53**	-

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) for $N = 193$. $r = .53$, $p < 0.01$ represent the statistically significant and meaningful Positive Correlation between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults.

Table 3

Correlation between Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Adults

	<i>Age Factor</i>	<i>Psychological Well-Being (PWB)</i>
Age Factor	-	.24**
Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)	.24**	-

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) for $N = 193$. $r = .24$, $p < 0.01$ represent the statistically significant and meaningful Positive Correlation between Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Adults.

Table 4

Correlation between Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and All Six Dimensions of PWB

	<i>LoR</i>	<i>AF</i>	<i>Auto</i>	<i>EM</i>	<i>PG</i>	<i>PR with Others</i>	<i>PL</i>	<i>SA</i>
LoR	-	.05	.39**	.43**	.37**	.19**	.39**	.35**
AF	.05	-	.20**	.22**	.16*	.26**	.05	.19**
Auto	.39**	.20**	-	.40**	.43**	.26**	.52**	.53**
EM	.43**	.22**	.40**	-	.41**	.47**	.53**	.62**
PG	.37**	.16*	.43**	.41**	-	.30**	.65**	.48**
PR with Others	.19**	.26**	.26**	.47**	.30**	-	.32**	.41**
PL	.39**	.05	.52**	.53**	.65**	.32**	-	.53**
SA	.35**	.19**	.53**	.62**	.48**	.41**	.53**	-

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Symbolic Representation in table; Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor (AF), Autonomy (Auto), Environmental Mastery (EM), Personal Growth (PG), Positive Relations with others (PR with others), Purpose in Life (PL), Self-Acceptance (SA). Table summarize the values of r and p for 193 Number of participants (N), represent the statistical significance of relationship between variables.

Table 5

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) Among Adults

<i>Variable</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>95% CI</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	1.995	.224	[1.553, 2.437]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.534	.062	[.413, .655]	.518	<.001
Age Factor	.344	.094	[.159, .529]	.218	<.001

Note. $R^2=0.326$, $F(2, 190) = 45.883$, $p<.001$.

Table contain unstandardized coefficient B , Standard Error (SE), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), significance (p) values.

Table 6

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Autonomy

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p
Constant	2.008	.314	[1.388, 2.628]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.510	.086	[.340, .680]	.386	<.001
Age Factor	.376	.132	[.116, .636]	.186	<.005

Note. $R^2=0.190$, $F(2, 190) = 22.318$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient B , Standard Error (SE), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), significance (p) values.

Table 7

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Environmental Mastery

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p
Constant	1.659	.299	[1.069, 2.249]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.537	.082	[.375, .699]	.119	<.001
Age Factor	.391	.125	[.144, .539]	.200	<.002

Note. $R^2=0.223$, $F(2, 190) = 27.206$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient B , Standard Error (SE), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), significance (p) values.

Table 8

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Personal Growth

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p
Constant	2.502	.313	[1.884, 3.102]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.475	.086	[.305, .644]	.367	<.001
Age Factor	.287	.131	[.028, .546]	.145	.030

Note. $R^2=0.161$, $F(2, 190) = 18.211$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient B , Standard Error (SE), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), significance (p) values.

Table 9

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Positive Relations With Others

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p
Constant	2.525	.313	[1.907, 3.143]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.224	.086	[.054, .393]	.179	.010
Age Factor	.418	.131	[.222, .740]	.252	<.001

Note. $R^2=0.100$, $F(2, 190) = 10.530$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient B , Standard Error (SE), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), significance (p) values.

Table 10

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Purpose in Life

Variable	B	SE	95% CI	β	p
Constant	2.540	.313	[1.932, 3.157]	-	.000

Level of Resilience (LoR)	.506	.086	[.336, .675]	.393	<.001
Age Factor	.074	.131	[-.184, .333]	.038	.571

Note. $R^2=0.157$, $F(2, 190) = 17.672$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient *B*, Standard Error (*SE*), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), *significance* (*p*) values.

Table 11

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting the Impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Self-Acceptance

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	95% <i>CI</i>	β	<i>p</i>
Constant	2.139	.307	[1.533, 2.746]	-	.000
Level of Resilience (LoR)	.436	.084	[.269, .602]	.345	<.001
Age Factor	.329	.129	[-.175, .583]	.171	<.012

Note. $R^2=0.153$, $F(2, 190) = 17.210$, $p<.001$

Table contain unstandardized coefficient *B*, Standard Error (*SE*), Standardized Coefficient Beta (β), *significance* (*p*) values.

DISCUSSION

Conclusion and Discussion on findings of the current study is part of this section. Discussion on what are the findings of current study, how they fit with the existing knowledge and how the findings contradict with previous research findings and why they are different from previous research findings. Since, the current study collected data from Pakistanis studying or working in different institutions, Descriptive Analysis was administered by using SPSS to understand the description of Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Current Research Participants, as indicated in Table 1 (see Results) the Number of participants or Sample Size is **193**, variables such as **Age Factor** represent that relatively a great number of participants fall into younger age category, **Gender** indicates nearly balanced between male and female participants in the study, **Educational Level** of participants in the study were approximately symmetrical, **Employment status** was slightly unequal due to participants holding different types of occupations such as employed fulltime, unemployed, student, House maker and relatively new types of occupations such as self-employed (entrepreneurs, online self-employment). Hence, the participants are not only from single type of Employment status, **Marital Status** suggested most participants in the study are single, **Household Members** indicated that larger households are more common it may be due to collectivistic culture (Joint Family System), or population, **Living Status** indicated that a big part of participants are living with their parents or relative (which might include guardians and in-laws) again enable the idea of collectivistic culture in Pakistan, Additionally, the majority of

participants in the study reported that they often engaged in stress reducing techniques. This gives an idea that there might be an increase in awareness, concern, and self-care related to Mental Health in Pakistani Society as compare to past.

Furthermore, now this section discusses and conclude the findings to assess that Is the results answer the research questions and fulfill the aim of the current research? The aim of the current study is to explore the deeper insight of association between Level of Resilience, Age Factor and Psychological Well-being. For this purpose correlation analysis was administered by using SPSS for three variables: Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB). The results shown in Table 2, and Table 3 (see Results) suggested that there is a significant moderate positive correlation between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Overall psychological Well-Being (PWB) and the effect size is Moderate to Strong between these two variables, but Age Factor has weak positive correlation with Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults. By analyzing this association the current study answered RQ1, that is to find Is there a significant relationship between Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and Psychological Well-Being (PWB)?

Additionally, another correlation analysis was run as shown in Table 4 (see Results) to assess the association between Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB): **Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations With Other, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance** to get deeper insight about this

association and to answer current study's RQ2, that is to find Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Resilience (LoR), Age Factor and all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? The interpretation of results implies that:

- 1) All Six Dimension of Psychological Well-Being (PWB): Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Others, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance has a significant positive correlation with Level of Resilience (LoR).
- 2) Two dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB): **Autonomy and Environmental Mastery** has the strongest association with Level of Resilience (LoR) among the all Six Dimensions.
- 3) There is a significant and meaningful association found between Age Factor and Five dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB): Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Others, and Self-Acceptance.
- 4) There is no significant and meaningful correlation found between Age Factor and **Purpose in Life**, one dimension from Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB).
- 5) All Six Dimensions are strongly interconnected or correlated with each other. Which support the theoretical structure Coral Ryff's Six Dimension Model of Psychological Well-Being.

Above findings support the current study conceptual framework that all Six Dimensions: Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Others, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance are interconnected and explains Overall Psychological Well-Being among adults and Level of Resilience (LoR) has a significantly positive and meaningful association with both Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) and all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-being which means adults with higher the Levels of Resilience (LoR) also have higher levels on all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB). In contrast, this is not the case for Age Factor because older adults also score somewhat better in Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) but the

association between Age Factor and Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) is positive and meaningful but weak. Even Age Factor has been found to be not correlated with Purpose in Life, one Dimension of Psychological Well-Being (PWB). According to the findings of De-Juanas et al., (30) study on individuals aged from 16 to 21 from Spain, Bogotá and Madrid revealed that Age has a significant moderate positive correlation with Purpose in Life but this study done on individuals who live in individualistic culture or society that is quite opposite of collectivistic culture in which individuals are interdependent on each other in many aspects of life regardless of Age as compare to Individualistic culture where Age plays vital role to become independent in many aspects of life such as decisions making and deciding profession or career to peruse, purpose in life. This same study also shows Autonomy is highly correlated with age, but the current study findings imply that Positive Relations with Others appears to be significantly correlated with Age in Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) this again shows that culture difference in context of perception of independence and Psychological Well-being (PWB) (30).

Furthermore, Multiple Regression Analysis was administered by using SPSS as shown in Table 5 (see Results) to assess the impact of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on Overall Psychological Well-Being. Results of this administration indicated that both Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor are significant and positive predictor of Overall Psychological Well-Being with **32.6% of variance** which means Adults who has better Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) is due to their higher Level of Resilience and belongs to older age groups in the Study which shows the relevance of Age Factor in the current study to predict Overall Psychological Well-Being. Noted, that Level of Resilience (LoR) it still has more impact than Age Factor to Predict Overall Psychological Well-Being. This facilitates the current Study to answer RQ3, that is, Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB)?

Moreover, this results also indicates that some other factors are also involved in this process or Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of individuals in the current study has significantly due to other factors which might be Social

Support, connectedness with significant others, or maybe due other factors that has adverse effects on mental health of individuals such as current political and economic crisis of Pakistan, scarcity of resources and inflation, perceive lack of control over environment. All these factors or some other factors might have more significant impact on Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among Adults in the context of Pakistan current situation. (51) There might be a cultural difference arise during the current study because there is are limited studies available on Resilience and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) association in Pakistani culture and most of the previous studies assess this association on individuals from different culture background such as Arabic-African culture (38-39,52), Italian culture (53-55), European culture (30) as compare to Pakistani culture these cultures are significantly different in context of self-concept, perceiving things, making judgments about self and self-discipline. So, this might be the case that Overall Psychological Well-Being is predicted due to other factors in Pakistani culture, not simply because of Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor. Unlike previously discussed studies in background section, the findings of the current study didn't reflect that simply Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor impact Psychological Well-Being (PWB) among adults, but there are some other factors that need to be taken into account to completely understand what major factors are the predictor of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) in Pakistani adults?

Additionally, another Multiple Regression Analysis was run to develop deeper insight about this predictable relationship Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor on all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB): **Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations with Other, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance.** The Findings facilitate to answer study's RQ2, that is to find Whether the Level of Resilience (LoR) and Age Factor Impacts all Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB)? The interpretation of results implies that:

- 1) The findings showed that both Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.386, p<.001$) and Age Factor ($\beta=0.186, p=.005$) were significant positive predictors of Autonomy. This suggested that higher Level of Resilience (LoR) and older age which shows Age Factor are associated

with higher levels of Autonomy. Although, Level of Resilience (LoR) had a stronger effect on Autonomy compared to Age Factor (see Table 6).

- 2) The results revealed that both Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.419, p<.001$) and Age Factor ($\beta=0.200, p=.002$) were significant positive predictors of Environmental Mastery. This indicated that higher Level of Resilience (LoR) and older age which means Age Factor are associated with greater Environmental Mastery. Whatsoever, Level of Resilience (LoR) had a stronger influence on Environmental Mastery among the predictors (see Table 7).
- 3) According to the results, both The Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.367, p<.001$) and Age Factor ($\beta=0.145, p=.030$) were significant positive predictors of Personal Growth. This suggested that higher Level of Resilience and older age which means Age Factor are associated with increased Personal Growth. However, Level of Resilience (LoR) had a stronger impact on Personal Growth than age (see Table 8).
- 4) The findings showed that both Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.179, p=.010$) and Age Factor ($\beta=0.252, p<.001$) were significant positive predictors of Positive Relations with Others. This implies that individuals with higher Level of Resilience (LoR) and older age which indicate the Age Factor reported that they have stronger Positive Relations with Others. In this particular, Age Factor tends to have greater impact on Positive Relations with Others as compare to Level of Resilience (LoR) (see Table 9).
- 5) The finding of the current study revealed that Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.345, p<.001$) was a significant positive predictor of Self-Acceptance, indicating that higher Level of Resilience (LoR) is promoting Self-Acceptance. Moreover, Age Factor ($\beta=0.171, p=.012$) was also a significant positive predictor founded in the analysis, suggesting that as age increases, Self-Acceptance improves (see Table 10).
- 6) In this particular case, Analysis revealed that Level of Resilience (LoR) ($\beta=0.393, p<.001$) was a significant positive predictor

of Purpose in Life, implying that higher Level of Resilience (LoR) is linked with a stronger sense of Purpose in Life but Age Factor ($\beta=0.038$, $p=.571$) did not significantly predict Purpose in Life. This implies that Age Factor has little to no direct impact on this dimension of Ryff's Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) Model (see Table 11).

CUNCLUSION

Current research findings are extensively constructive to address the gaps or limitations of previous researches that were conducted on the Level of Resilience, and Psychological Well-Being among adults. This study also beneficial to provide insight about predictable relationship between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Six Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being. In context of Pakistani Society, Limited Literature is available about predictable Relationship between the current study variables. This study address the limited existing literature by adding more insightful details about Level of Resilience (LoR) and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults. Previously studies collected participants from similar background, profession, or qualifications. So, the data is collected for the current study from Pakistani adults working and studying in various settings to address this issue in previous researches, but this lead towards issues related to sampling and data collection from participants. Like other studies, the current study also has some methodological limitations which were highlighted in this section. First is the data collection and analysis process is quite problematic due to number of items in the questionnaire which act as an obstacle during the data collection increase the chances of fatigue effect on the participants. So, it was quite complicated to deal with the Fatigue effect, reduce its impact of responses of participants and selecting data for analysis which are free from fatigue effect. Second is the potential factors that might influence the findings of the study, but it is beyond the scope of the current study is to assess the impact of these factors or to overcome their impact on the overall study. These factors might be individual's family and social support system that might impact on Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults because Pakistan is a collectivistic culture society, there is possibility

that other factors such as social support, relationship and bonding with parents, spouse, children and other family members and satisfaction with these relationships might also influence Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults. Those participants who reported high on Overall Psychological Well-Being (PWB) also reported high on Level of Resilience but there one dimension Positive Relations with Others is relatively high as compare to other dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB). Other potential factors also include current situation of Pakistan. Currently, Pakistan is facing political and economic crisis for more than three years. So, this might also impact participant's mental health and might influence their perception of control over their environment, negatively impact Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults. Third is the cross-sectional method which is used to collect data during the current study that might not provide the complete representation of relationship between Level of Resilience, Age Factor and Psychological Well-being (PWB). So, longitudinal study method might explore more constructive insight about this relationship and especially, for Age Factor Variable because this can develop insight about how people emerge or change over period of time, such as how Age Factor affect Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of participants throughout different age's. Forth is some Socio-Demographic factors that might affect the participant's diversity, make data to more generalizable to specific communities of Pakistan and negatively affect overall generalizability or diversity of participants of the current study. Such problems are that majority of participants are from one city Karachi, so it will be problematic to generalize these findings on overall Pakistani Society. Furthermore, Sample size of the current study is almost equally divided between male and female which provide an understanding of gender balance in the study which reduce bias and identification of gaps in human knowledge, but participants are not equally divided on age category, marital status, members of households which might influences the findings. Most participants are younger adults in the current study, has more than five households members, and major chunk of participants are not romantically involved with significant others which means they hold marital status-single these factor might impact the study.

This section of the study discuss how the findings can employ in the further studies and suggestions to address the limitations of the current study. Current study is beneficial to provide insightful literature about association between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults. This literature can aid future studies to develop more understanding of this association and explore more detail understanding of this association by adding some more factors that might be influencing Psychological Well-being (PWB) of Pakistani adults in a moderating or mediation factors conditions. Such as this study develop an insight that participants that has high Psychological Well-Being also has high Level of Resilience, but additionally participants reported that their Positive Relations with Others are significantly higher as compare to other Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being (PWB). This phenomenon can provoke the thought to develop more understanding into this relationship and assess other variables that might influence the Psychological Well-Being (PWB) in Pakistani Society.

Furthermore, limitations of current study such as fatigue effect can be address by using short measures that are statistically reliable. Additionally, adding incentives, keen monitoring of fatigue addressing that on the spot, utilizing of tools that assess information and avoid repetition this will limit the time of data collection process and eventually reduce fatigue effect in future studies. Potential factors as disuse in limitation section, might influence this association can address in further studies by studying all these variables in a single study to develop insight about this relationship or putting other variables as control variables in future study. Issues with cross-sectional method which is used to collect data during the current study that might not provide the complete representation of relationship between Level of Resilience, Age Factor and Psychological Well-being (PWB). So, employing longitudinal study method might explore more constructive insight about this relationship and especially, for Age Factor Variable because this can develop insight about how people emerge or change over period of time, such as how Age Factor affect Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of participants throughout different age's. Employing longitudinal method will resolve this problem for

future researches aims to explore age related changes in Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani Adults. Issues related diversity and generalizability can also be address in future studies. Such problems are that majority of participants are from one city Karachi, so it will be problematic to generalize these findings on overall Pakistani Society, this issue can be address by collecting data from different cities and communities and equally divide the sample size between major populated cities and communities of Pakistan. Additionally, issues regarding participants selection for study such as current study participants are not equally divided on age category, marital status, households members which might influences the findings, this can be address by selecting participants almost equally for these categories to reduce bias in future studies.

Discussion on future implications of the current study is also part of this section. The current research provides literature for researchers that are aim to study Psychological Well-Being (PWB) and it's predictors among Pakistani Adults. The main focus of this section is to identify the possible practical implications of current study in life or in context of future researches that will possibly aid by the findings of current study. Current research findings fits with the existing knowledge in a way that Level of Resilience (LoR) is a predictor of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults. This finding will provide an insightful knowledge to programs that focusing on developing Resilience-based therapeutic interventions to deal with psychopathology and promoting Psychological Well-Bing of adults.

Furthermore, nowadays, researchers are more focus on developing intervention programs and strategies to help individual to deal with stress and change. Thus, the current study will develop more insight about the relationship between resilience and psychological well-being which will help the researchers to work on their intervention programs. Such Resilience-focused interventions programs involves:

- 1) **Psychotherapy-based resilience programs:** works on problem-solving skills, mindfulness, psycho-education about stress among children and adolescents (56). This program is beneficial to enhance momentary well-being, decreasing symptoms of psychopathologies, and promotes

individuals ability to recover from adversity (57).

- 2) **Comprehensive soldier's fitness** is a training program for every soldier, family members, defense agency. The CFS models will incorporate five dimensions of fitness; (1) physical, (2) family, (3) social, (4) emotions, (5) spiritual. (58)
- 3) **The Master Resilience Trainer** is a training designed to teach resilience & performance optimization skills to unit personals & their family. (59)
- 4) **A pedagogical Framework for Leaders to Create a culture resilience:** To build Self-Efficacy (resilience by doing, vicarious resilience, resilience via interpersonal support, physiological self-regulation. (60)

So, the current study will provide valuable insight into association between Level of Resilience (LoR) and Psychological Well-Being (PWB) for evidence-based practice of above mention strategies to develop resilience among adults. Current study results also provide a support to imply that Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Six-Dimensions Model is fit to interpret Psychological Well-Being of Pakistani adults. Future studies can also do in-depth analysis of this association by using longitudinal methods and adding more variables as control variables, moderating variables, mediating variables to develop deeper understanding about Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults and this study aid future studies by providing impactful literature because limited literature is available on Psychological Well-Being (PWB) of Pakistani adults.

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